

GOIZ REFLEX THE IMPORTANCE OF THE RIGHT HEMIBODY IN MEDICINAL BIOMAGNETISM

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Micheline de Oliveira¹

Renata Chauvière¹

Angela Mara Rambo Martini²

Adriane Viapiana Bossa²

Jefferson Souza Santos³

ABSTRACT

The Shortening of the Right hemibody (SRH) is a phenomenon that occurs in Medicinal Biomagnetism (MB), a technique developed by Isaac Goiz Durán from the 80's. This method makes use of the static magnetic field (SMF) generated by a negative magnet applied to the skin in a dysfunctional anatomical region, out of its physiological balance, tending to alkalinity, which leads to the consequent contraction of the muscles of the right hemibody (RH). The elongation of the hemibody or muscle relaxation occurs when the point that receives the influence of the SMF is dysfunctional towards acidity caused by physiological imbalance. The shortening or elongation of the RH is a reflex called magnet-foot reflex, magnet-sympathetic-foot reflex or Goiz Reflex (GR). The objective of this study was to carry out a narrative review in order to demonstrate the importance of RH for the technique, identifying the neuromuscular response mechanism that

leads to the contraction or relaxation of the musculature. It was concluded that the GR is the main tool for energy diagnosis, confirmation and treatment of Biomagnetic Pairs (BMP). Its neuromuscular mechanism, similar to strength tests (a form of applied kinesiology), possibly results from the activation of different brain regions: cerebral amygdala, frontal and parietal lobes and areas corresponding to those stimulated with the SMF, promoting a reflex that, like the withdrawal reflex, is unconscious and qualifies the response in a binary way (stimulated area positively or negatively polarized). Its accuracy may be subject to interference from the information or semantic field of the therapist and the patient. The RH is more susceptible to manifest the GR which could occur on both sides. The GR concept was revisited over the years of MB development, a new science in constant evolution, and despite being a tool whose use and effectiveness have practical evidence, it is necessary to produce scientific evidence that proves its neuromuscular mechanism.

Keywords: Medicinal Biomagnetism; Biomagnetic Pair; Shortening of the Right Hemibody; Magnet-Sympathetic-Foot Reflex; Goiz Reflex; Magnet-foot Reflex; Integrative and Complementary Therapy; Magnet; Static Magnetic Field.

1. INTRODUCTION

In the middle of the 20th century, Biomagnetism emerged as a science when experiments were carried out to determine the influence of the magnetic field on health. This happened first in plants and animals and later in human bone tissue, assuming that osteogenesis is due to an endogenous electrical process. However, “the first thing to understand is that when a magnetic field acts on an organism, it acts on a set of substances, among which water – which in its pure state is extremely complex – is the absolute majority” (MADROÑERO, 2003, 2004).

The magnetic field produced by a magnet is static. It differs from the variable or dynamic magnetic field present in cellular devices, microwaves and pulsed magnetic fields because its strength (measured in Gauss) does not change over time as we see in magnetic resonance devices, bullet train tracks or the Earth's own magnetic field (XU *et al.*, 2017). The static magnetic field (SMF) sets in

motion materials endowed with magnetic properties (electrons, atoms, ions and molecules) generating bioelectricity (MADROÑERO, 2003, 2004; LEAL FERREIRA, 2004). Likewise, a region where the pH is unbalanced and which becomes a “living battery”, when set in motion by the action of the SMF, stimulates the return of the region to its state of physiological balance (MADROÑERO, 2003, 2004).

Medicinal Biomagnetism (MB) was developed and structured by Isaac Goiz Durán from 1988 after his participation in the first Biomagnetism Seminar given by Richard Broeringmeyer in Guadalajara. At the event, Broeringmeyer exposed the bases of “Energy Therapy” that considers the bioelectromagnetic aspects of man and the levels of pH distortions (potential of hydrogen) in an organism as determinants of his state of health or disease. His theory and practice were developed during his work at NASA (National Aeronautical and Space Administration of North America), based on the observation of the negative influence on the health of astronauts who presented various dysfunctions after being exposed to the absence of the magnetic field. Therefore, the phenomenon of Shortening of the Right Hemibody (SRH) was observed showing the existence of polarization related to the body's pH (FRANK, 2017; CASTEJÓN, 2015). The therapy developed by Richard consists of the application of a South polarity SMF (positive) on a region presenting pH distortion tending to alkalinity, in order to stimulate organic function and promote analgesia; or North (negative), whose properties are antibiotics, on a region presenting distortion, tending to acidity, in order to cure, for example, infections. Such use allows, therefore, to restore the body's health (BROERINGMEYER, 1991; GOIZ 2014a).

Based on this knowledge, Isaac Goiz Durán developed a technique that allowed to verify the existence of a point with pH distortion and its resonant corresponding point in the opposite polarity. These unbalanced codependent points form a Biomagnetic Pair (BMP). The technique consists of the application of an SMF of North polarity (negative) on a region presenting distortion tending to alkalinity. The shortening of the right hemibody (SRH) is the result. This indicates the need to find the resonant point, which will be in a region presenting distortion tending to acidity. At this second point, the SMF will be

applied in the opposite polarity, South (positive). At both poles there is the same intensity, cellular frequency and the same number of altered particles (CASTEJÓN, 2015).

Figure 1: Thymus-Rectum BMP

Caption: SMF of North polarity (negative / black) is applied to the skin on the Thymus gland region, where distortion tending to alkalinity was found. SMF of South polarity (positive / red) is applied to the skin on rectum region, where distortion tending to acidity was found. The action of the SMF will provoke the ions to displace causing a clash between the repelled particles, stabilising the pH in each region where the existence of nocive microorganisms won't be supported. The result is the treatment of the biomagnetic pair thymus x rectum, the first one to be discovered by Isaac Goiz Durán in 1988.

Source: Par Magnético Institute Archive. Images courtesy of Adriane Bossa.

According to Frank (2017), the scanning or examination that generates the Goiz Reflex is a variation of “applied kinesiology (AK) or muscle testing, a common technique among chiropractors, naturopaths and practitioners of integrative medicine”, being a method of “clinical utility”, that is, BMP “are identified by muscle testing”.

Muscular manual tests based on AK have been used since 1915 because they are able to assess different aspects of health (ROSNER, 2012), accessing the neuro-musculoskeletal system directly (CUTHBERT, 2007; JENSEN, 2015; PFISTER, 2018). AK produces an excitatory or inhibitory stimulus in anterior motor neurons from the spinal cord. Muscle hand tests designate a reflex or change in the central or peripheral nervous system (ROSNER, 2012). Today, they use a score of 0-5 by the Medical Research Council in the United States and 0-10 on the Kendall scale in addition to the manual dynamometer (PFISTER, 2018).

One of the most scientifically investigated AK tests is known as the Bi-digital Ring test, O-Ring test or BDORT, which was patented in 1993 by Yoshiaki Omura. Created in 1981, the test allows not only diagnosing the state of health of an internal organ, but also checking the dosage or suitability of a medication (LU *et al.*, 2014a; 2014b) to treat an organ, placing the object in the patient’s hands to be tested. Thus, its electromagnetic field interacts with the patient’s producing a force response. This test, which “allows a non-invasive diagnosis of pathologies or allergenic substances or the verification of appropriate medications for a patient” is widely used as a complementary diagnostic tool (OMURA, 1993).

From the perspective of the science of ontopsychology, the interaction between the semantic field (information) of the health professional and the patient, brings the possibility of conscious or unconscious communication between them and can interfere with the result (CARVALHO, 2019). Some researchers consider that the evidence of the accuracy of the AK application and the validity of the muscle strength test is not enough (KELSO, 2019), however, the B-DORT tool is widely adopted and recently, during the Covid-19 pandemic, supported diagnoses to doctors of different specialties. Its application could contribute to the early identification of disease severity, overcoming laboratory access. In addition, it was

also used in other diseases to verify medication dosages (PRADO *et al.*, 2021). 85% accuracy has been proven in other studies (OMURA, 1993; ESTRÁZULAS *et al.*, 2019)

The muscle strength test is a tool that measures the interaction between two electromagnetic fields. The GR is the result of the interaction between the applied SMF and the body, which is also a bioelectromagnetic system and it assumes the interaction between the professional performing the test and the patient. Therefore, GR can be analyzed by the same principles as the muscle strength tests.

Allopathy makes use of several tests to measure blood pressure, frequencies or electrical conduction in the body, as well as to check its health or illness state. Likewise, the MB uses the Goiz Reflex as a tool to measure the bioenergetic energy produced by different concentrations of hydrogen or free radicals (GOIZ, 2014a). The neuromuscular response mechanism leading to the Goiz Reflex (GR) allows the right hemibody (RH) to detect the bioelectrical dysfunction points and the resonant points that form the BMP. The pairing of the RH with the left hemibody (LH) evidences both the absence of pH distortion or bioelectrical dysfunction, as well as the treatment of BMPs after impaction by SMF. The RH and its alterations are the diagnostic method used by professionals who practice Medicinal Biomagnetism (MB). The treatment of the MB through the application of the SMF is based on the results obtained through the GR, hence the need to carry out scientific productions with a focus on this tool.

The present study aims to demonstrate the importance of GR, identifying the neuromuscular mechanism that produces this phenomenon.

2. METHODOLOGY

This research is a narrative review of which data were collected during the years 2021 and 2022 in electronic databases such as The Virtual Health Library Online (BVS), Google Scholar and Pubmed. Articles having a DOI (Digital Object Identifier) were prioritized, guaranteeing the credibility of the sources. The Boolean operators “and” and “or” were used.

The descriptors were: Medicinal Biomagnetism, Goiz Durán, Electromagnetic Field of the Heart, Cerebral Amygdala, Parietal Lobe, Frontal Lobe, Sympathetic Reflex, Bi-Digital O-Ring Test (BDORT), Autonomic Muscle Test, Bioelectromagnetism and Sympathetic Reflex and the combinations between these.

The theme directly linked to Medicinal Biomagnetism does not have abundant literature available. Therefore, several theses produced and published as a book with the support of the *Universidade de Chapingo* or the *Universidade de Nuevas Ciências Médicas*, under the tutelage of the creator of the technique, Dr Isaac Goiz Durán, were used. Publications by physicians and researchers who continue to study MB were included. Some authors mention the use of MB, however, they are not clear about the methodology or material. Due to the scarcity of material specifically linked to the technique, the latter was not considered as criterion for exclusion. In the other themes, articles were used following the criteria mentioned above.

Inclusion criteria were the following: priority for publication date from 2017 (about 5 years) or more recent for descriptors whose results were greater in number; from 2012 (about 10 years) in the descriptors whose scientific production is more scarce; languages of scientific production in Portuguese, English, Spanish or French.

Exclusion criteria were scientific production in other languages or without translation available directly in the databases, or addressing research fields not relevant to the main research topic.

3. RESULTS

A total of 41 sources were used, complying with the aforementioned criteria and respecting Law No. 9,610 of February 19, 1998, (Brazil), which legislates the copyright of authors, published on the government website <https://www.gov.br/pt-br/intellectual-property/legislation/copyright-legislation/national-legislation/law-no-9-610-of-19-of-february-1998.pdf/view>. Some publications covered more than one descriptor (Table 1).

Table 1: Main outcome of the research papers:

Descriptors used:	PubMed	Google Scholar	BVS	Used
Medicinal Biomagnetism “AND” “OR” Goiz Durán	95	2350	5	15
Heart’s electromagnetic field	142	42	141	4
BDORT “OR” Muscle resistance testing “OR” O-Ring	44	17500	132	11
Function of the Cerebral Amygdala	17472	12900	288	6
Function of the Parietal Lobe	13013	17500	1156	6
Function of the Frontal Lobe	40777	21700	2326	6
Sympathetic Reflex	2878	17800	3313	3
Bioelectromagnetism	452	1940	15	4

Source: The authors

4. DISCUSSION

The human being is a complex of bioelectromagnetic systems whose cells have positive and negative charges in constant movement to maintain their balance. The application of a static magnetic field (SMF) in a region with an imbalance of charges, with or without the presence of pathogens, is a natural option that allows restoring the body’s natural balance correcting the existing pH distortions. It induces the movement of ions internally (from the point of imbalance tending to alkalinity to the point of imbalance tending to acidity and vice versa) causing a clash between the repelled particles which promotes the treatment of the biomagnetic pairs (BMP) (GOIZ, 2014a; FRANK, 2017). In the hundreds of pairs already identified until recently (there were 75 in 2008 and

today there are approximately 476 BMP), the response of the right hemibody (RH) makes it possible to carry out its treatment effectively, producing results of improvement in the patient's health (GOIZ, 2014a / BOSSA, 2021/22).

The convention practiced in the MB is as follows: the north pole of the magnets is negative (black color) and the south pole is positive (red color). The negative polarity has anti-inflammatory properties and is attracted to the geographic North pole of the Earth (or its magnetic South). The positive polarity has analgesic properties and is attracted to the geographic South (or magnetic North of the Earth) (GOIZ DURÁN 2014a; GOIZ MARTÍNEZ 2018). MB uses magnets with more than 1,000 and up to 7,500 Gauss to detect and treat these dysfunctional points. The treatment of the BMP is verified when the patient's feet are paired after inducing the SMF with a magnet over one of the previously resonant points, in the same way of the point of distortion detection. The RH response qualitatively defines the organ. During pH distortion, it exhibits contraction/shortening or relaxation/elongation. In the absence of distortion it exhibits symmetry with the left hemibody (pairing of the feet) which is also observed after treatment of BMP (impaction by SMF). This response makes it possible to perform diagnosis and treatment of BMP identifying the etiology of the disease as well as its signs and symptoms, as can so many tests and complex examinations of allopathic medicine. The MB "fully identifies 100% of specificity of microorganisms and, depending on the therapist, 100% sensitivity to define the etiology of the disease without the need for laboratory studies" (GOIZ, 2014a).

The shortening of the right hemibody (SRH) can exceed 2.5 cm. If the patient's degree of hydration is higher, the reaction is more pronounced (FRANK, 2017). The search for dysfunctional points is called scanning. According to Isaac Goiz it is possible to scan with the north or south pole of the magnet but the north pole (negative) moves more energy and is unique, while the south pole (positive) has a smoother action and is multiple (GOIZ, 2014a). This statement indicates that a point on which the north pole is applied (negative/black) will have one resonant point on which the south pole (positive/red) will be applied but if the scan is performed with the south pole it may have two or more resonant points to which

the north pole is to be applied, which will increase the level of difficulty of the scanning.

By providing the organism with a chemical, electrical or physical stimulus, the neuromuscular excitability of a tissue is provoked, as the membrane potential before at rest is transformed into an action potential (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Stimulus Leading to Muscle Contraction

When the action potential reaches the neuromuscular plate, it releases calcium from the sarcoplasmic reticulum which, thanks to the presence of adenosine triphosphate (ATP), binds to troponin, producing the interaction of cross-bridges between myosin and actin, thus allowing the muscle contraction. If calcium is absorbed, it will cause relaxation. The volume of calcium flow and the volume of exchange of other ions generating ATP determine muscle excitability and the central nervous system excitability and the action potential that activates the muscle plate will be more or less rapid.

Source: EFDeportes.com, Digital Review. Buenos Aires – Year 17 – Nbr. 169 – June 2012. <http://www.efdeportes.com/> – Adaptation of the scheme by the students

The SMF generates a permanent current resulting in the chain of reactions (Figure 2) causing the contraction or relaxation of the RH (CASTEJÓN, 2015). Biomechanically, the process involves the action of agonist and antagonist muscles and possibly involves all muscle groups on one side of the body.

The neurologist Henrique de Juan called the phenomenon of shortening or elongation of the right hemibody (RH) a Magnet-sympathetic-foot reflex (CASTEJÓN, 2015). The intention was to highlight the triad involved in the process: the magnetic stimulus, the involvement of the Peripheral Nervous System and the foot reflex, because initially he used his feet exclusively to observe the asymmetry caused. In 2015 he honored Goiz Durán, naming it Goiz Reflex (GR) (CASTEJÓN, 2015).

The SRH phenomenon is used as a diagnostic tool for MB. Moisés Goiz Martínez, psychologist dedicated to research related to the MB compares the organism's response in muscle tests to artificial language based on binary code. He mentions recent research results indicating that nervous communication takes place under the same (binary) basis and "it is not strange that SRH (by the action of the BMP) is a form of communication that follows a procedure with the same binary characteristic (positive-negative)". He concludes that the contraction or relaxation of the RH are qualifiers of an organ or tissue in dysfunction, out of its physiological balance tending to alkalinity or acidity (GOIZ, 2014b).

The RH response, however, is not limited to the lower limbs but takes place as a whole. In Figures 4 and 5, Isaac Goiz Durán is teaching a course and carrying out a scanning in practice. It can be seen that he uses both lower and upper limbs as a reference:

Figure 3: Patient in sitting position

Figure 4: Patient in supine position

Caption: In Figure 3 with the patient sitting, the reference is the lower limbs; in Figure 4, the GR is perceived in the upper limbs, showing that the RH responds as a whole.

Source: Adriane Bossa's personal archive.

The sympathetic nervous system (SNS) and parasympathetic nervous system (PSNS) innervate the same viscera. They primarily have antagonistic functions, so that the overexcitement of one disturbs the balance between the two. Western allopathic medicine makes use of a series of reflex checks through tests and maneuvers performed daily in the office to assess the CNS (oculocardiac reflex, ciliospinal reflex, pilomotor reflex, neurological Buck reflex or patellar reflex test, etc.). Goiz Reflex also allows the exploration of the same system (CASTEJÓN, 2015).

In Isaac Goiz's assessments of the biomechanical response of the right hemibody, the conclusion was that "the left hemibody (LH) does not undergo the same variations because the electromagnetic current generated by the autonomous activity of the heart travels the LH 80 times per minute under normal conditions. This is the reason why only the RH response serves as a bioenergetic frame of reference to understand and identify BMP", that is, "LH remains stable because each beat of the heart depolarizes it by producing an alternating electromagnetic wave" (GOIZ, 2014a).

Three studies corroborate Isaac Goiz Durán's theory by differentiating the cellular environment of right (RH) and left (LH) hemibody and the influence of the left

and right cerebral hemispheres. The first study was on chronic heart failure in which patients were clinically evaluated on their body composition through a tetrapolar electrical bioimpedance analysis (hand, wrist, ankle and foot electrodes). It was verified that the “resistance on the right side” was 10 ohms lower than on the left side and the reactance was also lower, “as a consequence, the phase angle is significantly greater (almost 0.1 degrees) on the right side than on the left side (MASSARI *et al.*, 2001). The phase angle varies from 0° to 90° and assesses the health and cellular integrity according to the amount of water contained in them, which makes it possible to estimate the condition of the cell and its level of nutrition. Consequently, the higher the phase angle, the healthier the organism.

The impedance or electric flow passes through the biological medium having two components which are resistance and reactance. These are the two properties evaluated where the first verifies the displacement of the electric current related to tissue water and the second is the retention of electric energy “through the insulating effect of cell membranes, which act as energy condensers” (GARLINI, 2017).

The second study is by Foster *et al.* and addresses the effects of dopamine in patients with Parkinson’s, which, despite not being conclusive or controlled, brings interesting data regarding laterality. In this study, it was verified that the right hemibody (RH) responds better to dopamine and that, when the disease starts in the left hemisphere, it progresses more slowly. Among the hypotheses raised in this study, the “left hemisphere would be more able to compensate (the right side of the body) than the right hemisphere (to compensate the left side of the body) due to its greater capacity to regulate dopamine” because it has more dopaminergic innervations, compensating for the fact that the disease becomes symptomatic from the “loss of 70-80% of dopaminergic neurons – the left hemisphere then has an advantage over the right (FOSTER *et al.*, 2009).

In the third study also by Foster *et al.* (2011), it is stated that “the left and right cerebral hemispheres appear to have different roles in the regulation of cardiovascular functioning. While the left hemisphere is primarily associated

with regulation of the parasympathetic nervous system, the right hemisphere is associated with regulation of the sympathetic nervous system” which modulate heart rate (FOSTER *et al.*, 2011).

Figure 5: The Goiz Reflex in Picture

Caption: A1 – point without alteration or after treatment of BMP; A2 point examined out of physiological balance tending to alkalinity with RH contracting and A3 point examined out of physiological balance tending to acidity with RH relaxing.

Source: Par Magnético Institute Archive. Images courtesy of Adriane Bossa.

A self-analysis is when the operator applies the technique on himself/herself. According to Isaac Goiz, in this situation, the area of the anterior poles of the brain of both hemispheres (possibly the superior and middle frontal gyrus – region of the prefrontal cortex) are activated (GOIZ, 2014b). If the patient’s organism receives the information from the SMF and it is his body that responds through the GR, would the same area be activated in his brain? In the same work, it is also emphasized that the shortening or elongation is due to “the total sum of RH cells” (GOIZ, 2014b).

As a physiotherapist, Isaac Goiz came across individuals with asymmetries in the lower limbs. During his research and development of the MB, many of the cases of asymmetry actually indicated the existence of distortion in the kidney on the side of the shortened leg. In this pattern, the kidney is more acidic in resonance with the contralateral parietal lobe, which would be more alkaline. This BMP is called Goiz pair and when treated, corrects the existing asymmetry promoting feet pairing. After the treatment of this BMP, the scanning can be performed.

Subsequently, other resonant points were found to be impacted contra-laterally to the kidney if the parietal impaction did not resolve the asymmetry: ear, parathyroid or parotid. Up to the date of the consulted edition of “El par biomagnético” no other organ was found that caused this type of asymmetry (GOIZ, 2014a/2016). Could it then be the parietal lobe responsible for the GR? Or maybe one of the mentioned resonant points that also correct asymmetry?

Anatomically, the harmony of the functioning of each cell, tissue, organ and system is given by vital and metabolic feedback controlled by the SNS (controls voluntary functions) and PSNS (controls involuntary functions), which are autonomic and vegetative responding respectively by fight and stress reactions and rest and digestion reactions. These systems are reinforced by other neurological systems that have a certain amount of autonomy: the nervous system of the heart, the enteric nervous system and the cranial nerves. All these, even if they are in harmony and synergy, do not justify the contraction or elongation of the RH (GOIZ, 2014b).

David Goiz Martínez suggested that the shortening (or elongation) would be due to the possibility of contracting matter (or expanding it) in the face of a bioelectromagnetic stimulus. Its action would change the size of subatomic particles by distancing or approximating them or the atoms that form the molecules. This observation is based on the fact that negative bioelectric charges stretch matter while positive ones contract it (GOIZ MARTÍNEZ, 2015a). Later, he refuted this hypothesis, formulating his Shortening Theory (Goiz Reflex – GR) and justifying that the name “shortening” is used for historical reasons, since in the beginning it was believed that “all the matter of the leg that contracted”, which, “is not possible according to the laws of physics”, because if that were the case, it would reach the point of the foot in question “getting out of the shoes during scanning”, instead of what actually happens, which is a “longitudinal shortening with medial dorsiflexion of the foot”. For this reason, he suggests the name Contraction Theory, as it is the leg muscles, especially the iliopsoas, that produce hip flexion and a slight external rotation of the muscle, generating movement and performing traction on the bone structure of the pelvic limbs (Goiz Martínez does not address GR in the upper limbs as can be seen in Figures 3 and 4).

According to him, this is the justification for the effectiveness of the Goiz pair, as the kidney of the shortened hemibody is at the same height as T12, which is inserted in the iliopsoas, which is controlled by the contralateral parietal artery, precisely where the second magnet of this pair is placed. In this way “the popliteus, greater common flexor of the fingers and tibialis posterior muscles contribute to extending the foot externally and internally rotating the ankle inwards”. According to his theory, these movements refer to an innate withdrawal reflex and the result of the survival instinct generated by fear (probably, when fleeing, our ancestors had to climb trees and to perform this action with ease, speed and support, they rotated their feet internally). Currently, the same muscle contraction reflex is reproduced in response to stress, however, “only on the right side because of the predominance of the left cerebral hemisphere, since this has greater irrigation, oxygenation and electrical activity”. The SMF applied in a certain region, when making the electrical stimulus, causes the change in the bioelectric field to reverberate in the organism as a whole, which is perceived at an instinctive level by the cerebral amygdala, a structure that is part of the limbic system where fear is processed (GOIZ MARTÍNEZ, 2015 b).

Whenever a stimulus related to survival instincts is received, the cerebral amygdala participates. The organism can adapt to the existence of a distortion that will become its new point of balance. The application of the SMF threatens this “unbalanced stability”, thus activating the survival instinct, the amygdala, and then cerebral cortex, as well as the peripheral nervous system or neurocortex (GOIZ MARTÍNEZ, 2018; BOSSA 2021/22). It is known, however, that SMF applied to the body is painless. This fact excludes the possibility of nociceptor reflex activation that is a response to a painful stimulus. Nevertheless, considering that the SMF activates the RH musculature in its entirety, the stimulus must activate the dorsal neurons in the spinal cord after having activated the cerebral amygdala and the interneurons that will distribute the neural connections in the medulla region and subsequently distribute it between the regions of agonist and antagonist muscles in a cross-type reflex (BEAR *et al.* 2017). The crossed reflex, however, would indicate that the left hemibody should respond to the stimulus of the right cerebral hemisphere in the same way.

David Goiz Martínez (2018) coined the term “magneticception” (magnetic perception or *magnetocepción* in Spanish), adapting the word proprioception to sensitivity and reactions to magnetism, creating the Theory of “Magneticception”. According to him it is the reflex of neurophysiological withdrawal (referring to the GR) “produced by the activation of distinct brain areas in the face of the bioelectric reaction in the organism, generated by the presence of a SMF in a place with alteration (excitability)”. The brain areas most reactive to stress stimuli and sensitive to changes in electricity are the Amygdala and the left parietal lobe, which, when stimulated, send signals that cause muscle contraction or relaxation in the RH after activating the spinal bulb where 90% of the motor fibers intersect. The GR is more evident in the pelvic limbs because they are symmetrical, long, with a greater contractile response and easier technical handling by the professional; the tilt of the pelvis occurs due to the effect of contraction and relaxation directly affecting the iliopsoas, causing asymmetry. According to Goiz Martínez, the response is observed on the RH because most people are right-handed, which indicates a predominance of the left hemisphere (GOIZ MARTÍNEZ, 2018). The MB application methodology, however, does not recommend using the left hemibody as a reference in left-handed patients. About the left hemibody, David Goiz (2018), emphasizes that its contraction is considered atypical and when it happens, recommends reversing the polarity of the magnet to produce a shortening or elongation of the RH (which implies the mobility of both hemibodies), or simply taking the left hemibody as a reference to performing the scanning, considering this a neurophysiological variant (GOIZ MARTÍNEZ, 2018).

“By positioning a magnet at a point of bioelectromagnetic alteration, a reaction is produced in the bioelectric system of the body, which consequently causes a sudden change in the interaction of electrical charges in motion and the flow of electrons, which is perceived in an intelligent and selective way in the organism (body), due to its magnetic-reception and proprioception capacity, generating an alert

interpretation in the cerebral tonsils that increase the neuronal sensitivity and excitability conducive to the activation of the predominant parietal lobe in the brain, which leads to the contraction of several muscle groups of the contralateral hemibody, as a withdrawal reflex, typical of the survival instinct of several species that adopt a position of protection or withdrawal reflex” (GOIZ MARTÍNEZ, 2018).

The study by Ocklenburg and others (2022) addresses the difference in the size of the amygdala, indicating that this fact could be due to time, emotional valence (linked to positive or negative emotions) or perception properties (OCKLENBURG *et al.*, 2022). “In different studies and research questions about the amygdala, a frequently encountered finding is that the left and right amygdala are not equivalent in terms of function and structure” (OCKLENBURG *et al.*, 2022). Would such a difference have a direct effect on the right (RH) or left (LH) hemibody? Allen *et al.* (2020) mention that the right and left cerebral amygdala play different roles with regard to pain processing, with the “first being pro-nociceptive and the second currently considered anti-nociceptive”. There is an anatomical lateralization in response to nociceptive stimuli that, being detected in the RH, is processed in the left hemisphere and vice versa (ALLEN *et al.*, 2020). Considering that the SMF focusing on a point causes stress, generating a similar response to the pain stimulus, the predominance of the RH response in relation to the LH could be justified with the research by Allen and others who mention that “as the pain persists, overactivation of neurons in the right central amygdala disappears and returns to baseline spontaneous activity, and neuronal excitability in the left increases to lead to pain relief. This balance between left and right cerebral amygdala activation is, therefore, able to modulate acute pain, which is important for detecting potential damage; nociceptive signals warn of potential damage and protect damaged tissue during healing, but eventually cease when the stimulus is removed or healing is complete” (ALLEN *et al.*, 2020).

Still considering SMF exposure as a stressor that would activate the fight-or-flight mechanism, according to Simic and others (2021), “specialized neuronal populations in various parts of the cerebral cortex, notably the anterior cingulate, the anterior insular, prefrontal ventromedial and subcortical structures such as the amygdala, the ventral striatum, the putamen, the caudate nucleus and the ventral tegmental area” are activated regions in this mechanism of response to emotions (SIMIC *et al.*, 2021). Maldonado and others (2020) describe that the responses that lead to the fight-or-flight mechanism are “regulated by connections between the amygdala and the periaqueductal gray matter” and that the interconnected areas involved include “the amygdala, the prefrontal cortex, the hippocampus, midbrain, brainstem nuclei, anterior pituitary, and hypothalamus having similar functions in rodents and humans. They further describe that the “autonomic nervous system is also stimulated in response to fearful stimuli, activating the cardiovascular system (increased blood pressure and heart rate) through increased connectivity between the amygdala and the locus coeruleus, the main source of noradrenergic innervation of the brain” (MALDONADO *et al.*, 2020). Since fear, as well as stress, are reactions that generate a similar response to that of exposure to the SMF, by activating the autonomic system, would the body be equally affected bilaterally?

Goiz Martínez divides pelvic limb shortening into 3 types where 90% are physiological. These are sustained by the involuntary and sustained contraction of a muscle group. The patient’s hydration level and emotional state directly interfere with this type of shortening. This physiological shortening is subdivided into spontaneous, chronic and acute. This classification responds to the patient’s emotional or mental stress, respectively: mild and that does not require the impaction of points for correction or the following (chronic and acute) that require it because the patient’s stress level is high. The other 1 to 5% are anatomical or structural and result from an innate or acquired asymmetry. The remaining 5 to 10% are of mixed or musculoskeletal type and account for the combined characteristics of the two preceding types. The use of Goiz pair mentioned above can correct the first one but it will not be effective on the last two (GOIZ MARTÍNEZ, 2018). According to David, the contraction or relaxation

response can be present in both the right and left hemibody. Both sides of the body are susceptible to asymmetry correction, thus both respond to the GR.

The GR is the most used kinesiological test in MB consisting of an involuntary contraction of a certain group of RH muscles (GOIZ MARTÍNEZ, 2018). In addition to being a reference for energy diagnoses and confirmation of exclusively MB treatments, the GR is also commonly used in treatments using combined techniques. Damyanov and collaborators (2019/2021) have been developing, for more than 12 years, a method combining MB therapy and Insulin Potential Therapy (BPT – Biomagnetic Therapy with Magnetic Pair and IPT- Insulin Potentiated Therapy) to treat cancer patients whose treatment with chemotherapy and/or radiotherapy were unsuccessful. With these two treatments they developed a protocol with positive results. The GR plays a fundamental role in the application of the protocol (DAMYANOV *et al.*, 2019a; 2019b; 2021).

In Applied Kinesiology or in manual muscle tests the patient is challenged with information (touch, pressure, emotional process, gustatory or olfactory sensation) producing a muscle response of increased or decreased strength (ROSNER, 2012). The SMF is the information used in MB and the response is contraction or elongation of the hemibody. According to Frank (2017), this information can also be a nutrient, supplement, pharmaceutical agent or anything else that the examiner wants to test, including the patient's organs and tissues via stimulation of the SMF. He states that the GR is more advantageous than muscle strength tests because the musculature is not fatigued by the examiner because it is not necessary to exert an opposing physical force on a given muscle group. In this way, all anatomical points, organs and tissues can be tested, BMP could be found and properly treated (FRANK, 2017).

In 2022 the XXI International Congress of Biomagnetism organised by the Isaac Goiz Durán School took place. Moisés Goiz delivered a lecture entitled “Why nature behaves according to mathematical laws”. One of the slides shared was of an encephalogram taken at the moment of the shortening of the right hemibody. The image showed areas from the left cerebral cortex exhibiting

activity where the frequencies were accelerated and which covered a diversified area about three times larger than that the ones in activity in the right cerebral hemisphere. The authors of the study were unable to obtain written authorization to use the handouts received afterwards. The authors made an approximate replica of it, as shown in figure 6.

Figure 6: Approximate replica of the figure exhibited at the XXI International Congress of

Caption: stressed area

Biomagnetism in October 2022 during the exhibition by Moisés Goiz.

Caption: The figure shows the following cerebral areas: superior and middle frontal gyrus in the left hemisphere, frontal and parietal lobes bilaterally, and different regions of the parietal and frontal lobes in the left hemisphere.

Source: The authors.

The information about parts of the body stimulated by SMF was not accessible to the public. It was exemplified that in situations of conscious stress resulting from concerns arising from everyday life, the areas of greater frequency respond symmetrically and at the moment of the shortening of the right hemibody the asymmetry is clear. According to him the body adapts to the distortions and the consequent imbalances become the new state of balance in a given organ or tissue. Exposure to SMF would be the stressor that would lead to GR as shown in the image above. The lecture was based on his research yet to be published. The replica of the image was included in this study given the importance of the event to MB and of the subject to the present study.

Among the hypotheses raised regarding the GR since MB started to be developed, it was seen that: only the right hemibody responds; the anterior brain area in both hemispheres is responsible for self-analysis (the operator scanning himself); the GR is given by the total sum of the right hemibody (RH) cells and/or that the parietal lobe is responsible for the reflex. As of 2014 (assuming previously published and later reissued books have gone through review), no justification has been found for the answer to why RH responds; the GR can be seen as a muscle strength test, but also as an involuntary neurological reflex, like the tests mentioned above. In 2015, the hypothesis of expansion or retraction of matter represented by subatomic particles arises. This theory goes back to that of the sum total of cells according to Isaac Goiz reported in “O Par Biomagnético” (The Biomagnetic Pair). In a publication afterward, David Martínez discards this theory to conclude that it is a matter of muscle contraction and relaxation with consequent retraction of the bone structure. In this conclusion, he reiterates the quality of a reflex similar to that of withdrawal and in response to the survival instinct, in addition to evidencing the joint participation of the amygdala and the parietal lobe. In 2017 Frank brings the idea of SMF information (positive or

negative charge) and the resulting response of contraction or relaxation of muscle groups, reinforcing the quality of the GR as a muscle strength test. In 2018 Goiz Martínez states that both sides of the body can exhibit the GR and no longer addresses Isaac Goiz regarding the influence of the electromagnetic field of the heart interfering with the left hemibody response, a hypothesis indirectly supported in the research by Foster and others (2009, 2011) and by Massari (2001). In 2022, the electroencephalogram presented by Moisés Goiz showed different areas of the left hemisphere of the brain exhibiting stress and the activation of the cerebral amygdala was not clear. The cerebral amygdala participation was evidenced in the other studies that assume the response to stress generated by the SMF as a stimulus of the response of fight or flight.

5. CONCLUSION

In Goiz Reflex (GR), the right hemibody (RH) is the preferred reference to scan the body for imbalances in organs or tissues. It responds to the left hemisphere, which has a faster bioelectric flow, and is directly affected by the electromagnetic field of the heart causing the right hemibody to be more stable and thus more suitable to respond to SMF stimulus. In atypical cases the left hemibody may manifest the response as both hemispheres are stimulated during a scanning. As a neuromuscular response, GR results from the activation of the cerebral amygdala in a process similar to the fight-and-flight reaction, and cannot be controlled by a conscious process. The parietal lobes that promote the contraction or relaxation of the assessed hemibody and the areas corresponding to the investigated areas are also activated. There are no studies that determine with exact precision which areas of the brain participate in the GR and therefore, the neuromuscular mechanism involved in the process cannot clearly be determined. The reflex makes it possible to qualify the type of bioelectrical dysfunction of the investigated point (out of physiological balance tending towards acidity or alkalinity).

As it brings together the qualities of an involuntary reflex, a binary response as in the muscle strength test of applied kinesiology and for allowing the type of imbalance in the body to be qualified, the GR is the preferred diagnostic method

of the MB technique. It has been verified in practice that it makes it possible to identify the microorganisms that cause the signs and symptoms at 100% specificity and, depending on the therapist, it can define the etiology at 100% sensitivity. Even so, it is subject to the bioelectromagnetic field (semantic or information) of the professional and the patient, which can interfere with the results.

The Goiz Reflex has been explained in multiple ways, none of which have been presented as definitive. Therefore, it can be regarded as a theory, specifically the Shortening or Contraction Theory. Achieving an understanding of and providing evidence for the neuromuscular mechanism using appropriate technology would greatly contribute to justifying the accuracy of this diagnostic tool, as demonstrated in practical applications by Biomagnetism researchers.

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¹ Graduate Student in the Program in Biomagnetism and Bioenergy Applied to Health, Par Magnético Institute – IPM / Faculty of Governance, Engineering and Education of São Paulo – FGE. São Paulo, Brazil.

² Co-supervising Professor Program in Biomagnetism and Bioenergy Applied to Health, Par Magnético Institute – IPM / Faculty of Governance, Engineering and Education of São Paulo – FGE. São Paulo, Brazil.

³ Advising Professor Program in Biomagnetism and Bioenergy Applied to Health,

Par Magnético Institute – IPM / Faculty of Governance, Engineering and
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